

Data descriptions

1. Photo metadata

The 2 files names correspond with the photographer:

- **Laurito_metadata.PNG**
- **Hermant_metadat.PNG**

2. Skycharts

The altitude and the azimuth of the upward discharge are determined thanks to the software "carte_du_ciel" (version 2.76c) at the date/time of the luminous event and from the camera location

- file for the sky chart: **jet_starter_202211012219_hermant.cdc**
- file for the support image in sky_chart: **upward_discharge_202211012219_hermant.bmp**

3. Current moment waveforms

The data for the current moment waveform for the flash associated with the upward discharge is in the file called "**cmw_20221101_211942.475.txt**".

4. LMA data

The file for the LMA data associated with the flash of the upward discharge (21:19:42 UTC) is: **LMA_luminous_event.csv**

Animated file for the storm: **SAETTA_Flash_Anim_20221101_2005-colorp-200.gif**

Data for the VHF sources associated with the storm producing the upward discharge: file **LYLOUT_20221101-Serge-SOULA_CELL_jet.xlsx**

Profiles of the VHF sources each 10 minutes: file **minute20.png** shows the LMA VHF sources vertical distribution within the storm producing the luminous event, during 10 minutes between 20:15 and 20:25 UTC on November 1st, 2022. Same for the files:

- minute30.png**: 10 minutes between 20:25 and 20:35 UTC on November 1st, 2022
- minute40.png**: 10 minutes between 20:35 and 20:45 UTC on November 1st, 2022
- minute50.png**: 10 minutes between 20:45 and 20:55 UTC on November 1st, 2022
- minute60.png**: 10 minutes between 20:55 and 21:05 UTC on November 1st, 2022
- minute70.png**: 10 minutes between 21:05 and 21:15 UTC on November 1st, 2022
- minute80.png**: 10 minutes between 21:15 and 21:25 UTC on November 1st, 2022

5. Lightning flashes

The lightning activity from Météorage for the storm producing the upward discharge is provided in excel format:

File **Meteorage_Cellule_flash_up.xlsx** (the flashes are highlighted)

6. Meteorology

The file **Radiosondage.pdf** shows two atmospheric soundings in Ajaccio (Corsica) and Cuneo (Italy), on November 2nd, 2022, at 00:00 UTC.

7. Cloud top temperature

The data of cloud top temperature are available in the files "**meteosat_202211hhmm.dat**" with a delay of 10 minutes for the scan of the storm area (the parallax correction has to be applied with -0.14° in latitude).